

SELF-DISPERSION OF CARBON NANOTUBES IN THERMOPLAST POLYMER

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1 Introduction

Dispersing carbon nanotubes in a polymer matrix is a major challenge to improve the electrical and mechanical properties of carbon nanotubes polymer composites. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) agglomerate in solutions and the high viscosity of thermoplast polymers makes it difficult to mix in tubes (1). We have recently discovered, much to our surprise, that carbon nanotubes disperse spontaneously in Polyether ether ketone (PEEK) when annealing (2). PEEK is a high performance polymer, chemically inert and has a high thermal resistance compatible to the temperature range requirements for aircrafts. The high melting temperature (343°C) and strong adhesion of PEEK are challenging when making composites.

2 Context: CNT dispersion in PEEK

When annealing agglomerated CNTs on the surface of a sheet of PEEK it is observed that PEEK is wetting the CNTs and is incorporated in the polymer. The effect of annealing is assumed to make the polymer diffuse in the CNT agglomerate. PEEK contains oxygen groups which interact with the nanotube surface (Figure 1). It is known that molecular oxygen binds to single walled CNTs with adsorption energy of 0.25 eV (3) and the interaction of oxygen with the nanotube surface leads to hole doping. Furthermore the phenol rings in PEEK are compatible with the honeycomb lattice of the tube surface. Both these effects contribute that PEEK is wetting CNTs.

The diffusion of nanoparticles in a polymer matrix depends in general on size and shape of the nanoparticle. While the diameter of carbon nanotubes is comparable or smaller than the chain length of the polymer, the tube length is several

orders of magnitude longer. For individual nanotubes the mobility depends on diameter and length. The mobility of the CNTs in the polymer matrix is expected to be much smaller due to its large mass compared to the polymer molecule. Given the large length of CNTs they inevitably are bent depending on the local structure of the polymer and the presence of small crystallites in the vicinity of the CNT. Structural variations along the tube and its larger mass have the effect that vacancies are formed between the polymer matrix and the CNTs. The surface of CNTs is atomically smooth increasing diffusion of polymer molecules on its surface as long as the interaction with the CNT surface is small enough. The surface adsorption energy is about one order of magnitude larger than the thermal energy at room temperature. Since the PEEK molecules are chains they have the tendency to align with the CNT axis favouring diffusion along the tube axis. It has been shown through numerical simulations that the diffusion of polymer molecules along the tube axis is larger than in directions perpendicular to it (4). This means that the tube surface represents a preferential diffusion path for the matrix molecules. The diameter and length distribution of CNTs and the presence of other forms of carbon have the effect that the CNT agglomeration is disordered with frequent vacancies and gaps between the tubes. PEEK molecules have the tendency to diffuse into these vacancies limiting the bending of the tubes. This gives a possible scenario of how tubes get separated in a viscous polymer. When neighbouring tubes leave a vacancy behind, induced by bending motions, the vacancy gets filled in with PEEK having the effect of separating the tubes. The high temperature stability of PEEK makes it possible to keep the temperature of the polymer at elevated temperature favouring the effect of diffusion. This means the higher

temperature stability of PEEK implies the diffusion induced effects are playing a larger role and can be used to disperse CNTs.

Multi walled (MW) CNTs are conductors or small gap semiconductors and are excellent absorbers of electromagnetic radiation. The singularities in the electronic density of the quasi one dimensional nanotubes and the large range of diameters of the concentric walls make MW CNTs excellent broad band infrared and optical absorbers. The first optical transition energy in eV is given by $0.8/d(\text{nm})$ where d is the tube diameter. As the outer walls have a larger diameter ($>3\text{nm}$), the transition energies fall in the infrared spectral region. The absorbed heat is, however not well dissipated. Heat conduction in carbon nanotubes is mediated through phonons and is inefficient between CNTs. The small diameter of CNTs implies that effects of quantization of phonons perpendicular to the axis are strongly reducing heat conduction. In contrast the insulating polymer matrix has a much smaller optical absorption, several orders of magnitude smaller. The high absorption of electromagnetic radiation by the nanotube leads therefore to a heat backlog or imbalance and a heat gradient is formed around tube agglomerations. In addition the annealing process implies exposure to higher infrared radiation and as a result higher radiative heating. The higher temperature in the proximity of the tubes is correlated with a higher diffusion of the polymer molecules near and on the tubes. This means the action of diffusion is large were the tube are agglomerated. This contributes in making the dispersion more uniform. In summary, self-diffusion of CNTs in PEEK can be understood to be the consequence of enhanced diffusion in the vicinity of the tubes due to higher optical absorption of CNTs and preferential diffusion along the tubes of PEEK polymer molecules.

We will first present evidence that PEEK is wetting CNTs. We then show TEM and Raman spectral cross sectional images of a composite layer to show the uniformity of the CNT dispersion for multi walled CNTs (MWCNTs) and double wall CNTs (DWCNTs). Electrical conductivity measurements as a function of amount of CNTs dispersed on PEEK before and after annealing are discussed at the end.

3 Experimental

To get a better understanding of the self-dispersion process of CNT, we use transmission electron microscopy and Raman multi-spectral imaging. While transmission electron microscopy turns out to be limited when observing small diameter nanotubes in a polymer matrix, Raman spectroscopy can be used to monitor the tube dispersion at different scales (> 1 micrometer). Raman spectroscopy gives access to the vibrational mode such as the in plane out phase vibrational band of neighbouring atoms in carbon nanotubes located at 1600 cm^{-1} (G-band), a defect induced breathing mode at around 1350 cm^{-1} (D-band) and a less intense band at 1100 cm^{-1} (P-band) from PEEK. The intensity of the P-band is proportional to the crystallinity of the polymer. The D-band band position depends on excitation energy and shifts by $50\text{cm}^{-1}/\text{eV}$. From the shifts of the G band one can deduce strain in the carbon nanotubes and charge transfer or the doping level of the tubes (5). From the D band one obtains information about the number of defects or the crystallinity of the tubes. The high absorption of the illuminating laser when performing Raman spectroscopy by the nanotubes can lead to local temperature changes. This can be verified by comparing Stokes and Anti-Stokes spectra allowing determining the local temperature. Far from the electronic resonances the intensity of the band is proportional to the amount of CNTs sensed by the focal spot. The amorphous phase and luminescence give rise to a wide background signal. We record Raman maps by varying the step size between 1-10 micrometers to record the uniformity of the tube dispersion at different length scales. Double wall carbon nanotubes (DWCNTs) are particularly interesting when using Raman spectroscopy. For DWCNTs one can separate strain and charge induced spectral shifts and study doping effects (6).

The dispersion experiments were carried out at identical conditions. Solutions of known amount of DWCNTs in NMP were dropped on a PEEK sheet (4, 8 and 12 drops were 1drop: $0.4 \cdot 10^{-6}\text{g}$ of DWCNTs) supplied by Victrex Technology Center, UK. The samples were heated in Argon. Argon was pumped through the oven (size: $1\text{m} \times 2.5\text{cm}$) for 90 minutes (Argon flux = $0,16\text{ L/min}$) to avoid oxidation of the samples. The samples were annealed above the glass transition temperature of

the thermoplastic polymer (at 390°C) for 15 minutes (Figure 2). We have used MWCNTs from Arkema (Graphistrength C100) and DWCNTs from CIRIMAT, Institut Carnot, University of Toulouse as received. For TEM measurements all samples were placed in an epoxy matrix and cross sections were cut with ultra microtom equipped with a diamond knife in 100 nm thick slices. The slices were placed on Cu grids with a holly carbon film. TEM experiments were carried out on a transmission electron microscope Philips CM20 with an accelerating voltage 120kV. For Raman measurements we used the same samples in the epoxy matrix. Raman spectra were measured on an Xplora Horiba spectrometer using the 785nm excitation wavelength to reduce luminescence. Electrical measurements were performed using an electrometer from Keithley (model 6517B/E) and depositing two silver electrodes at a distance of 12 mm.

4 Discussion

Figure 3 shows SEM images of MWCNT powders before and after annealing. Before annealing the agglomerated tubes can be seen on the PEEK powder while after annealing the tubes are incorporated in the polymer and the surface is more uniform. Variations of the surface roughness are seen on the left and right side in the figure after annealing. This clearly shows that PEEK is wetting the CNTs after annealing. Figure 4 shows a SEM image of the PEEK surface after annealing showing the non uniformity at the surface at the scale of several micrometers. Annealing has the effect of increasing the crystallinity. To assess the structure and morphology of composite materials we use TEM and Raman spectroscopy. TEM micrographs provide a detailed view over several micrometers regions (Figure 5). At this scale MWNTs appear to be well-dispersed in the PEEK matrix. We also observe that the CNTs align along the interface of the composite layer and the bulk PEEK. Interesting a clear interface is formed between the composite and bulk PEEK. This suggests that PEEK is diffusing in the CNT agglomerate and the diffusion of the CNTs is negligible. In figure 6 we can see the carbon holly film with PEEK and the MWCNT/PEEK diffusion layer. We estimate the thickness of the diffusion layer to be between 2.5-3 μm from the TEM image.

When using DWCNTs it is much harder to make out the tubes due to their small diameter (~ 3 nm) compared to the structural fluctuations of the polymer (figure 7). Only the catalytic particles used for growing the DWCNTs can be seen in the TEM images. One can see that the catalytic particles are not dispersed in the composite layer. This shows indirectly the importance of PEEK interacting with the tubes and enhanced diffusion on the tube surface. No conclusion about the thickness of the diffusion layer can be made from TEM images. To estimate the thickness and homogeneity of the diffusion layer we use Raman spectroscopy as a complimentary technique to TEM.

Raman imaging was performed on polished surfaces of the composite. Figure 8 shows an example of a typical Raman spectrum obtained for PEEK+MW (a) and DW (b) CNT composites. The G ($\sim 1582\text{cm}^{-1}$) band is the zone centre Raman allowed mode corresponding to a stretching vibration of the two atoms in the unit cell of graphene. The D ($\sim 1350\text{cm}^{-1}$) and D' ($\sim 1620\text{cm}^{-1}$, weak intensity) bands are due to one phonon and two phonon defect assisted scattering. The vibrational mode of the D band corresponds to the out of phase breathing mode of neighbouring hexagons in the graphene lattice. The exact position of the D band depends on excitation wavelength and is the consequence of the linear electronic dispersion at the Dirac point (K point) and the double resonance scattering process taking place (7). That means, in plane LO and LA phonons, degenerated at the K point couple strongly to electronic states at the K point of the unit cell in reciprocal space. The line shape of the D band depends on the exact type of defects in the tubes and is not well established. In figure 8 one can see differences in relative intensity and spectral line width for the spectra of DWCNTs and MWCNTs. For MWCNTs the D band is more intense and both bands are broader. For DWCNTs the G band is more intense and the bands are narrower. This means the DWs contain less defects. This is mostly because the MWCNTs are produced at industrial scale while the DWCNTs are produced at smaller laboratory scale. We recorded spectra along a line of 12 μm , in steps of 0.02 μm across the diffusion layer to analyze its homogeneity. Figure 9 shows an optical image of the diffusion layer of MWCNT in PEEK and we see the results of the Raman spectral line scan. The Raman spectra are

plotted in horizontal direction and the intensity corresponds to the color in the image. The two lines seen in the diffusion layer correspond to the Raman D and G band. The uniform intensity of the G band across the composite layer shows that the tubes are homogeneously dispersed in the polymer matrix. This demonstrates that polymer diffusion and anisotropic heat absorption has the effect to disperse the tubes and lead to homogeneous dispersions from highly agglomerated tubes. The thickness of the diffusion layer can be estimated to be 2.5-3 μm . This is coherent with what we observe in the transmission electron microscope (Fig. 6). We notice that the Raman background signal is larger where there are no CNTs. The background signal is due to broadband luminescence in PEEK and epoxy and from amorphous carbon in the CNT sample. The fact that the luminescence signal drops in the composite layer indicates that photo excited charge carriers are efficiently quenched by the presence of the CNT network. This shows that we can use Raman spectroscopy to estimate the thickness and uniformity of the diffusion layer of MWCNT in PEEK. Figure 10 shows a similar Raman line scan when DWCNTs were dispersed in PEEK. For DWCNTs the G band is more intense and the D band is less uniform. From the uniform G band intensity across the layer we conclude that DWCNTs are homogeneously dispersed within the spot size of optical objective (NA 0.9) and deduce a thickness of the diffusion layer (1-1,5 μm). The defect induced D band intensity is less intense in the middle of the layer. It is not clear why there are more defects near the two interfaces. It could be that the tubes are more constrained near the surface. Its origin is not clear and needs further investigation. We notice that the thickness of the composite layer is smaller than we have earlier observed (1) which we attribute to the fact that we have used smaller amounts of agglomerated tubes on the surface of the PEEK sheet. Furthermore the G band extends further in the bulk of PEEK suggesting that a smaller amount of DWNTs with less defects are incorporated deeper into the bulk.

Electrical measurements were performed as a function of the number of droplets of DWCNTs in NMP evaporated on a given surface and before and after annealing (3.5 mg/m² droplet). The annealing had the effect that the electrical conductivity increased by one or two orders of magnitude. This

shows that the annealing process increased the number of conducting paths. This means annealing has the effect spreading larger agglomerates and increasing the amount of smaller agglomerates multiplying the number of connecting paths. When increasing the number of droplets of the NMP carbon nanotube solution on the PEEK surface the resistivity did not necessarily increase before annealing. It is found that the drying process of the droplets is not reproducible and leads to non uniform behavior when increasing the number of droplets and the tubes are in an agglomerated state. The conductivity increased by a factor of 20 when depositing a few droplets after annealing and to 150 times for 10-12 droplets. This shows that the conductivity increased with the amount of nanotubes deposited. The electrical conductivity is estimated, to vary between 0.04 S/cm and 1.20 S/cm for fields smaller than 10 V/cm when taking into account the thickness of the composite layer. Due to the non uniform deposition of the nanotubes, the dispersion is not uniform at scales of several 100 micrometers leading to variable thickness of the composite surface layer making it difficult to determine the electrical conductivity accurately. The conductivity is found to be linear up to a field of 10 V/cm and the current saturates reversibly for higher fields. Possibly junctions heat up at points where tubes are in contact having the effect of reducing the conductivity. But it is more likely that the current is limited because of increased electron scattering and phonon emission and backlog of acoustic phonons (8).

5 Conclusion

We have shown using SEM that PEEK is wetting CNTs powders. This is qualitatively explained by the presence of oxygen groups interacting with the CNT surface. Using TEM and Raman spectral imaging we show that a uniform composite layer and a clear interface is formed between the composite layer and the bulk. The formation of an interface between the composite layer and the bulk indicates that the polymer is diffusing into the CNT agglomerates. The formation of vacancies and very different optical and diffusion properties of the CNTs and the polymer is believed to have the effect to increasing diffusion in the proximity of CNTs and to separate the tubes leading to a homogeneous

dispersion. The fact that PEEK has a high melting temperature can be used to take advantage of diffusion of PEEK to separate the tubes. Self-diffusion of CNTs in PEEK can be understood to be the consequence of enhanced diffusion in the vicinity of the tubes due to higher optical absorption of CNTs and preferential diffusion along the tubes of PEEK polymer molecules. The thickness of the composite layer has been determined by cross sectional TEM for a MWCNT/PEEK surface layer. While TEM from DWCNTs in PEEK is challenging due to their small diameter, Raman imaging has been able to map the uniform distribution of the CNTs across the layer and it was possible to estimate the thickness of the composite layer. Electronic transport measurements show that annealing increases the conductivity by one to two orders of magnitude depending on the number of tubes deposited on the surface. The high electrical conductivity of 1 S/cm measured and the simplicity of the used dispersion process demonstrates much promise for using CNT/PEEK composites for electrostatic materials in fuel lines, filters, pumps and tanks, coatings, packaging and electromagnetic shielding.

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Fig. 1 Polyether ether ketone (PEEK) molecule.

Fig. 2 Schematic presentation of sample preparation: agglomerated CNTs are dispersed on PEEK sheet and annealed in argon atmosphere.

Fig. 3 SEM images of PEEK film with MW CNTs: a) before annealing MWCNTs on the surface of PEEK, b) after annealing PEEK is wetting MWCNTs.

Fig. 4 SEM image of PEEK surface showing variations in the uniformity at the micrometer scale.

Fig. 5 TEM image of MWCNT/PEEK composite. 15 minute annealing at 390°C of agglomerated CNTs on surface of PEEK. MWCNTs tend to be oriented parallel to the interface

Fig. 6 TEM image of MWCNT/PEEK cross sectional slice of the composite layer after annealing at 390°C for 15 minutes of agglomerated CNTs on the surface of a sheet of PEEK.

Fig. 7 TEM image of DWCNT/PEEK composite. 15 minute annealing at 390°C of agglomerated CNTs on surface of PEEK.

Fig. 8 Typical Raman spectra with D and G bands obtained for a) PEEK + MWCNT composite, b) PEEK + DWCNT composite. The D band at 1300 cm^{-1} is more intense the G band for MWCNTs while the opposite is observed for DWCNTs. The line width of the G band is narrower for DWNTs compared to MWCNTs.

Fig. 9 a) Optical image of diffusion layer of MWCNT/PEEK composite layer, b) Raman spectral line across the diffusion layer: the intensity and line width of G and D bands are uniform across the layer and the background signal due to luminescence is reduced in the composite layer.

Fig. 10 a) Optical image of diffusion layer of DWCNT/PEEK composite b) Raman line across the diffusion layer: the intensity and line width of G bands are uniform across the layer. The D band is more intense near the two interfaces.

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